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LANDMARC MAGAZINE

THE END OF
LANDMARC

THE START OF A
TRANSITION TO
SUSTAINABLE
LAND-USE

2025 SPECIAL ISSUE

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PUBLICATIONS

EDITOR'S NOTE

THE STORY OF LANDMARC

This magazine marks the end of the EU Horizon 2020 funded LANDMARC project. LANDMARC's mission was and is to store more carbon in soils and trees and limit land-use emissions, while preserving ecosystem services and improving biodiversity. The relevance and urgency of this mission cannot be overstated. Newly published research suggests a "large decline of the land carbon sink".

Delivering on three pillars

LANDMARC set out to deliver on three main pillars of research. **Pillar one** deploys methods and insights from social sciences and targets key stakeholder groups. The main aim was to map and better understand local contexts as well as to co-create

feasible future transition scenarios.

Pillar two uses a wide range of earth observation tools, methods and models. We designed novel combinations of these tools and field tested them to improve the monitoring of greenhouse gas emissions and/or carbon removals buffered in soils and trees.

Pillar three builds on the qualitative and co-created transition scenarios and aims to analyse the land use change and economic impact of scaling various carbon farming practices deployed in different regions and at different scales.

See **C10** on our publications page for more about how these pillars fit together.

People first (Pillar I)

When LANDMARC started back in July 2020, it set itself ambitious goals to advance the knowledge base for land-based mitigation technologies and practices (i.e. carbon farming/nature-based solutions).

Since LANDMARC started during the COVID pandemic, our plans for stakeholder engagement and co-creation activities had to be revised. Engaging effectively with stakeholders in these circumstances was something of a daunting prospect.

But it was encouraging to see the flexibility of all the people involved to adapt to this new reality. The entire research process underlined once more the importance of continued engagement and dialogue with stakeholders.

It is because of their insights, experiences and inputs that projects like LANDMARC are able to fine-tune their methods and approaches to conduct impactful research. Stakeholders are not just recipients of completed knowledge, they are a key source of co-created new knowledge. For more about this, see [page 32](#).

Better glasses (Pillar II)

Accurately and cost-effectively quantifying GHG emissions from soils and trees and the amount of carbon sequestered at different spatial scales (parcel, region, country, continent) is a big challenge.

In most cases, you need in-situ measurement tools to validate and calibrate (or 'ground truth') the data you get from your remote sensing tools.

A BIG THANK YOU FROM LANDMARC!

We'd like to thank the hundreds of stakeholders who so generously shared their (often indigenous) knowledge, experiences, successes and failures with us.

This project would not have been possible without you.

We sincerely hope that our joint efforts have provided you, your community and wider networks with the knowledge, tools and capacities that enables you to continue your journey towards more sustainable land use practices.

Over the course of the project, we developed novel combinations of earth observation tools – like drones, satellites and soil analysis – and field tested them for different land use practices in many countries around the world.

Our primary aim was to advance the science in this field. But we also developed these tools with possible commercial market applications in mind. The carbon farming market will become ever more relevant in light of recent policy developments like the EU's Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming Regulation (CRCF) and COP 29 on Article 6 of the Paris Agreement as well as the need to improve the national greenhouse gas inventory reporting for the land-use sector. More about this on [page 7](#).

Exploring what ifs (Pillar III)

Transitioning towards more sustainable land-use practices requires communities, policy makers, and individuals to work towards a long term vision and strategy.

This isn't easy, especially when the future is uncertain. Changing what we do today and replacing it with something new always raises a lot of 'what if' questions. Among many others, these include:

- What if we maximised implementation of peatland rewetting? What would that do to the economy?
- What if most of our farmers adopted organic/no tillage farming practices? What would this imply for our soil carbon status and soil health?
- What if we scaled up agroforestry and afforestation?

To explore these questions, we used a suite of earth system, land-use and economic models. These helped us understand the potential impact and contribution of scaling a wide range of land-based mitigation technologies and practices. See [page 21](#).

A breath of fresh air

Because of the Covid pandemic, it was only deep into our second year that the LANDMARC consortium was able to meet in-person for the first time.

By then, online meetings and virtual engagement had proven highly effective. But there is something quite special about meeting face-to-face.

During these meetings there was no shortage of enthusiastic people and happy faces. We also took the opportunity to go on field visits to carbon farming demonstrator sites.

These site visits provided the whole consortium with a hands-on perspective that was relevant for understanding the everyday challenges and needs of rural communities, and what it would take to implement and maintain a novel land-use practice.

You can read more about what we learned on these visits on [page 11](#).

Walking a mile in a carbon farmer's shoes

On 28 November 2024, we hosted one last a policy event at the House of the Dutch Provinces in Brussels.

During the event, (co-organised with two EU-funded sister projects, CONSECUS and RESCUE) we were able to talk about some of the insights we gained over the course of this project about the impact policy mixes have on ordinary carbon farmers.

We did this by taking the perspective of the

European carbon farmer, who will have to navigate through a complex landscape of interacting EU policy frameworks (e.g., CAP, ETS1, ETS2, RED, CRCF, CSRD, etc.) and national policy instruments to secure a decent future farm level income. Read more on [page 14](#).

Taking that extra step

COVID wasn't the only geopolitical event that affected our plans. Shortly after the Russian invasion of Ukraine, the LANDMARC consortium once again found itself reacting to a new geopolitical situation.

This reaction was both personal and professional. Some LANDMARC researchers were able to open their homes to Ukrainian citizens that fled to Europe.

But the war in Ukraine also deepened collaboration between LANDMARC and the National Scientific Centre, Institute for Soil Science and Agrochemistry Research (NSC ISSAR) in Ukraine.

Prior to the war, NSC ISSAR was one of the stakeholder organisations we were talking to, and looking for opportunities to collaborate with.

After the war began, this relationship deepened, resulting in some interesting research collaborations. We provide some detail about this on [page 28](#).

A WORD FROM LANDMARC'S COORDINATORS

In this editorial (and in the magazine more broadly) we've tried to tell the story of LANDMARC.

This isn't just a story about conducting research, producing reports and sharing results.

It's also a story about the personal ambitions and circumstances of all the people involved, and the efforts they made to contribute.

We hope this magazine provides a flavour of what LANDMARC has been all about.

Above all, we hope you enjoy reading it! It's been quite a journey.

Warm regards,

- **Jenny Lieu** – Assistant Professor at Multiple Actor Systems Department, TU Delft
- **Eise Spijker** – Senior researcher at JIN Climate & Sustainability

A NEW PAIR OF GLASSES

Earth Observation (EO) is like putting on a new pair of glasses for understanding our planet.

It involves gathering, analysing, and interpreting data about Earth's systems – its landscapes, climates and activities. This technology has come a long way since the 1800s, when cameras were first used to capture natural disasters and military scenes from above. Today, EO uses satellites, drones, and ground-based sensors to track changes in our environment at an unprecedented scale, helping us tackle challenges like climate change.

The Copernicus boost

The European Space Agency's Copernicus program has taken EO to the next level. Using high-resolution sensors, Copernicus supports everything from precision agriculture to disaster management. It can track agricultural cycles, monitor soil and water systems, and even detect crop health issues, reducing losses and boosting yields.

REMOTE SENSING: THE HEART OF EO FOR CARBON FARMING

Remote sensing means collecting information about the Earth's without physically touching it. It use tools like optical, radar and thermal sensors, as well as non-imaging sensors to measure atmospheric composition. It plays a vital role in carbon farming², helping track carbon storage and CO₂ absorption from space. As the tech evolves, its ability to monitor and support sustainable practices will only grow.

COPERNICUS: EARTH OBSERVATION FOR ALL

Copernicus is the EU's game-changing Earth observation programme, offering open, free data for agriculture, land mapping, water management, and more. It helps monitor irrigation, assess crop conditions, and track droughts, benefiting farmers, researchers, and policymakers alike.

The program's family of Sentinel satellites is specifically designed to meet the needs of users, delivering data that directly impacts productivity and policy decisions.

Building trust & traceability

With EO, transparency is the name of the game. Near real-time data from Copernicus satellites (updated every 2–12 days) can reveal whether farming practices are sustainable—or harmful. This helps landowners detect problems quickly and respond effectively. EO also underpins carbon credit certification by ensuring traceability, giving stakeholders confidence in climate-friendly initiatives. It also helps land-managers adapt to climate risks, like droughts, heatwaves, and shifting rainfall patterns.

CMMT-ELEAF MODEL

- **What It Does:** Developed by [eLEAF](#) and ETH Zürich, this model measures plant and soil carbon, combining direct forest measurements, advanced mapping technology, and remote sensing to estimate total carbon storage.
- **What its good for:** Calculating ecosystem productivity and carbon sequestration.
- **Benefits:** Comprehensive, large-scale monitoring of biomass and carbon capture using high-tech models and satellite data.
- **Where we've used it:** United States, South Africa, Burkina Faso, and the Netherlands.

Practical applications

Over the last four years, we have developed five different Earth Observations tools. These have not only been an invaluable source of data for our research, but are extremely useful tools for farmers and land-managers around the world. Here is a brief summary.

SMART AG

- **What It Does:** AgroInsider's SmartAG uses Copernicus satellite & field data to monitor, report and verify vegetation growth and health. It tracks carbon sequestration potential, verifies carbon credits, and ensures transparency in carbon farming activities—all while helping users adapt to changing climate risks.
- **Who Can Use It:** Anyone managing land (like farmers or forest caretakers), or monitoring carbon sequestration.
- **Benefits:** By combining satellite data with on-the-ground observations like photos and videos, it offers a clear, reliable, and transparent picture of farm condition—which is great for the credibility of carbon credit schemes.
- **Where we've used it:** Spain, Portugal, Ukraine, Indonesia, and the Netherlands.

SIF-GPP-CARBON SEQUESTRATION MODEL BY KNMI

- **What It Does:** This model uses satellite data to track how plants use carbon and how land use changes affect carbon storage globally.
- **What it's good for:** Helps understand carbon dynamics on a global scale and supports climate change mitigation efforts.
- **Limits:** Its accuracy relies on the quality of satellite data and specific regional conditions.
- **Where we've used it:** Australia and China.

FIELD-MAP FOREST INVENTORY-LIDAR MODEL

- **What It Does:** It uses forest measurements and LiDAR remote sensing to convert data on biomass and biodiversity into carbon storage values.
- **Benefits:** It's an accessible digital tool. It can evaluate the canopy height of dense forest stands more accurately than traditional tools.
- **Where we've used it:** Spain, Portugal and Germany.

BIOCLEAR EARTH PROTOTYPE

- **What It Does:** Bioclear Earth's now prototype currently analyzes soil health using advanced methods to study soil microbes and their carbon storage roles.
- **What its great at:** Provides detailed insights into soil microbial activity and overall soil health.
- **Limits:** The logistics of delivering soil samples and preservation solution outside Europe are challenging.
- **Where we've used it:** The Netherlands, Germany, Switzerland, Burkina Faso, Kenya, Canada, Indonesia, Spain, Portugal, Vietnam, Nepal, and Ukraine.

Conclusion

Earth Observation offers an incredible new perspective on our planet. It's transforming how we manage land, ensuring transparency and sustainability in carbon farming efforts. As this technology advances, it will shape a greener, more sustainable future for us all.

More on earth observation

- **Informal Articles**
 - C9, C15
- **Journal Articles**
 - A19, A21
- **Deliverables**
 - B5, B6, B7, B9

SWIMMING COWS

**WHAT ANIMALS CAN
TEACH US ABOUT
CLIMATE MITIGATION**

Jan den Besten ('De Groene Geer') explains the pressure drainage system at a peatland rewetting pilot site, at the Groene Geer organic farm in Nieuwland.

Fire-prevention is of goat importance!

AND FIREFIGHTING GOATS

One of the complexities of changing how we use land is that we aren't the only ones living on it. Animals live on the land too. Animals can be both more and less adaptable than us. Sometimes the needs of animals make the LMTs we studied more difficult to implement. But, surprisingly, sometimes animals can make implementation easier.

This is a lesson we learned during two research-in-practice fieldtrips for the whole consortium – one in the Netherlands in 2022, and another in Spain and Portugal in 2023.

In 2022, Consortium partner KNMI took the LANDMARC team to a nearby peatland rewetting pilot project at 'De Groene Geer', a mixed biological dairy farm in Nieuwland.

Increasing ground and ditch water levels in these low-lying peaty soils areas has a range of benefits. It helps limit soil CO₂-emissions and soil subsidence and improves biodiversity. But there are also trade-offs – especially for cows. Peatland rewetting can mean reduced grass yields and more challenging outdoor grazing conditions for cattle – meaning farms like the Groene Geer need a more innovative business model.

SWIMMING COWS AND THE NEED FOR REFORM

Even in the days of the Roman empire, the Dutch were famous for their cheese. But it wasn't until the 17th century that the dairy sector began industrialising. By using wind-driven watermills to manage water levels in low-lying (peaty) soils farmers were able to develop and expand the dairy sector in the Netherlands. But today, after decades of drainage that resulted in soil carbon loss and ongoing soil subsidence, these practices need reform. With an increasingly unpredictable weather and climate system (resulting in increased rainfall, rising sea levels and more frequent river flooding) there is an urgent need for a smarter and more sustainable water and land (carbon) management approach.

More on peatland rewetting

- [Deliverables](#)
 - B3, B4, B5, B8, B9,

FIREFIGHTING GOATS : A MODERN TWIST ON AN ANCIENT PRACTICE

Dehesas and Montados are man-made, agroforestry-landscapes in the Iberian Peninsula that date back as far as the 7th century. They typically have low tree density combined with some form of livestock foraging (cattle, sheep, goats, pigs). But ongoing climate change means the Iberian Peninsula is facing extended and compound hot and dry periods. This means practitioners need to adopt more climate resilient land management techniques. This could mean selecting more drought resistant tree species or (as we've discussed) using targeted livestock grazing to reduce the risks of uncontrollable wildfires.

More on agroforestry

- [Explainers](#)
 - C8
- [Deliverables](#)
 - B3, B4, B5, B8, B9
- [Journal articles](#)
 - A9, A15

So cows can make one kind of climate friendly land-use practice (peatland rewetting) more challenging. But, as we learned on a different visit, goats can make another climate friendly practice easier.

Megafires are a big worry in Spain and Portugal, which have dense forests and increasingly hot and dry weather conditions. But, as we learned during a 2023 site visit, goats can play a surprisingly important role in preventing forest fires.

In 2023, consortium members Ambienta and Agroinsider took us on several research-in-practice site visits to Montados and Dehesas agroforestry projects around Plasencia (in Spain) and Evora (in Portugal). This included a visit to the [MOSAICO](#) project, which adapts traditional agroforestry practices to reduce the risk of wildfires. Goat grazing is a big part of how this works. When farmers graze their goats in and around forests, this limits the natural re-growth of pine trees and the amount of biomass fuel available – creating fire breaks that make it harder for fires to run out of control.

ARE WE REALLY HELPING CARLA AND HENK?

A CALL TO SIMPLIFY THE MAZE OF CARBON FARMING POLICIES IN THE EU

Imagine you're **Carla** and **Henk**, Dutch dairy farmers ready to do your part for the planet.

You want to make your farm greener and more sustainable, but working out how to make it work financially feels impossible. Why? Because the policies and rules around carbon farming are tangled, and very difficult to untangle.

What is carbon farming?

Before we explain this, it's worth clarifying what carbon farming might look like.

Some options include:

- Reducing the amount of dairy cattle
- Using manure to produce biogas
- Planting trees on their land and implementing agroforestry practices
- Rewetting peat soils to lock in carbon
- Growing alternative crops like fibres for biomaterials
- Changing the menu of their dairy cattle
- Switching to organic fertilizers or biochar in their soils
- Applying no tillage farming methods

All of these practices are good for the environment, but bad for revenue. So there are schemes in place designed to support farmers like Carla and Henk financially if they decide to take up these practices.

But actually applying for that support is harder than it needs to be.

This is why both the strategic dialogue on the future of EU Agriculture and the EU CRCF initiative have pointed out that there's a clear need to limit the administrative burden for Europe's carbon farmers.

Caught in the policy web

At the EU level, there are plenty of relevant

policy initiatives for farmers looking to go green. But these programmes have their own rules, registries, and paperwork.

For farmers like Carla and Henk, this means that on top of their regular work managing a dairy farm, they would need to match each carbon farming activity with the right funding programme.

Each programme requires forms, reports, and navigating different digital platforms. Miss a step, and they might lose financial support altogether.

More complexity

Applying to more than one scheme isn't only a matter of filling in the same forms twice.

Initial mapping of the policy, MRV-C and registry landscape for EU carbon farmers

Many of these schemes have inconsistent rules and goals, which makes reporting to more than one of them complicated.

Take greenhouse gas accounting for example. Different programs calculate emissions reductions in different ways, even when they're looking at the same farm activity. This means farmers need to do double the work to meet the requirements of multiple programs.

Even if they manage to navigate the system, there's the risk of administrative bottlenecks—where data overlaps, or worse, gets counted twice. These inefficiencies add costs and headaches for everyone involved.

Hidden costs

This complexity makes carbon farming more expensive than many policymakers have accounted for.

Suppose Carla and Henk decide to go for peatland rewetting, agroforestry and fibre cropping.

It's unlikely they would be able to receive support for these activities without hiring multiple auditors and advisors, at considerable expense.

Doing it on their own would mean understanding the technical and operational implementation of entirely new on-farm activities (which might also involve significant upfront investment).

It would also mean figuring out which incentive schemes are the best for them to apply to. This isn't obvious.

WHAT CAP, ETS-1, RED, ETS-2, CSRD, CRCF, AND AG-ETS HAVE IN COMMON

- They are mostly performance-based (not activity-based).
- Each has its own scheme-specific monitoring, reporting, verification and certification (MRV-C) requirements.
- They assign a price (bonus or penalty) to emitting, reducing GHG emissions or removing atmospheric CO₂.
- They often overlap with other farm-related bio-economy activities.

HOW THEY DIFFER

- They use different GHG accounting rules (e.g., system boundaries and sector coverage).
- They operate different registries.
- They target different sustainability goals.

For example, they could try to get finance for peatland rewetting and agroforestry via the voluntary carbon market (under CRCF) or eco-schemes (under CAP).

If they wanted support for fibre cropping, options include the eco-schemes (CAP) or going via a public tender for construction stored carbon (under CRCF).

Of the EU policy frameworks, the CAP is probably the best known. But it's also being reformed regularly.

And there are also ongoing revisions to the EU energy and climate policy frameworks (CSRD, CRCF, ETS-2, Ag-ETS, RED) in the evolving circular bioeconomy.

Staying up-to-date with those developments is challenging even for experts. It's not something we could realistically expect of busy farmers.

So in all likelihood, Carla and Henk would need to hire multiple consultants and auditors to advise them on the pros and cons of the available schemes, match them to the scheme that is best for what they want to do, and help ensure they are in compliance. This would not be cheap.

How to help

To make things simpler, we need a streamlined system that works for farmers, not against them.

Here are a few ideas:

1. **Create a digital navigator tool:** Develop a user-friendly app or online tool that helps farmers understand which incentives and policies apply to them, all in one place.
2. **Simplify the Rules:** Reduce the number of programs farmers need to juggle or integrate new ones into existing frameworks.
3. **Standardise Processes:** Make it so that one set of data can meet the requirements for multiple programs, cutting down on duplicate work.
4. **Decouple MRV from Funding:** Design systems where financial support isn't tied to specific MRV requirements that might differ from those used by other schemes.
5. **Build in interoperability.** Make sure that systems for tracking greenhouse gas reductions and green claims, such as national and EU level registries, and can work with each other and handle cross-border transactions smoothly.

By making these changes, we can free up farmers like Carla and Henk to focus on what they do best: running sustainable farms that help both their communities and the planet.

POLICY LESSONS

BEYOND SIMPLIFYING CARBON FARMING

Over the last four years, we've explored promising policy mixes for scaling up land-based mitigation practices (LMTs) in 14 diverse case study countries.

Drawing from targeted literature reviews, stakeholder consultations, and policy analysis frameworks, we developed context-specific recommendations tailored to each

country's unique circumstances.

This makes it difficult to come up with insights that apply to every country. What works in Germany may not suit Nepal.

But some broad themes and patterns did emerge that might be useful for policymakers wherever they are.

SIX KEY POLICY LESSONS

1

Align Policies Across Sectors:

Ensure agricultural policies complement objectives in forestry and other land-use sectors. Misaligned policies can lead to unintended consequences. For example, forest conservation policies in Indonesia may shift agricultural development to secondary forests or wetlands, undermining environmental goals. Similarly, in Europe, increased biochar production could escalate biomass demand, risking unsustainable forest harvesting.

2

Invest in Local Capacity:

Limited technical, financial, and human resources at local levels—especially in developing nations—present significant barriers. Capacity-building through education, technology transfer, and funding is essential to enable effective implementation of land-based mitigation technologies (LMTs).

3

Focus on Co-benefits:

LMTs that deliver additional benefits, like biodiversity conservation, improved livelihoods, and enhanced soil fertility, are particularly worth pursuing. For instance, biochar and agroforestry were standout examples of co-benefit-rich solutions in several case studies. Tailoring to local conditions is key.

4

Avoid One-Size-Fits-All Policies:

Strategies should be tailored to each country's unique ecological, economic, and social contexts. For example, while Sweden might prioritise BECCS for negative emissions, agroforestry looks a better option for Burkina Faso. Generic approaches risk inefficiency and reduced buy-in from stakeholders.

5

Strengthen International Collaboration:

Cross-border cooperation is crucial to ensure land-use policies in one country don't conflict with those of its neighbours. Collaborative frameworks can enhance both the effectiveness and the fairness of mitigation efforts.

6

Protect Vulnerable Populations:

Land-uses changes risk placing undue burdens on vulnerable groups. For instance, restrictive land-use regulations could drive up food prices or threaten livelihoods. Joined up thinking is needed to avoid this. Climate policies need to align with policies on food security and economic growth.

Our policy research

- **Journal Articles**
 - A10, A11, A12, A21
- **Deliverables**
 - B12, B14, B16
- **Explainers and Consultations**
 - C2, C9, C11, C12, C13, C14, C15

BIGGER ISN'T ALWAYS BETTER

At LANDMARC, we've been modelling how land-based mitigation technologies and practices (LMTs) can help limit global warming to 1.5°C. Our work revealed some unexpected results.

We analysed four LMTs—afforestation/reforestation, agroforestry, reduced tillage, and bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS)—under two scenarios: high and moderate ambition.

The high ambition scenario assumed land-based mitigation would be a top priority for governments. It assumed strong regional engagement on scaling up these practices, and large-scale implementation. It also assumed a large reduction in the amount of land needed for food production, based on

crop yield improvements and dietary changes.

The moderate ambition scenario assumed less regional integration, and that governments would also have other compelling priorities to consider when it comes to land-use. It also assumed we'd need more land for food than in the high ambition scenario.

Surprising results

Both scenarios showed that LMTs substantially reduce atmospheric CO₂, but cannot meet the 1.5°C target by themselves. Surprisingly, however, the difference in outcomes between the two scenarios was modest.

Implications for policy

While these are just one set of modelling results, they do suggest that scaling up LMTs would be a very good idea for policymakers. Even more easily achievable moderate scaling can deliver meaningful benefits while balancing priorities like biodiversity and food security.

Find out more

If you'd like to hear more about these particular results, more detail about these findings is in **Project Deliverable** currently under review by the European Commission, and in articles we are preparing to submit to peer reviewed publications. Please [get in touch](#) if you'd like to learn more.

See the next page for more about our modelling work.

HOW WE CALCULATED THIS

For this global analysis, where we looked at the effects implementing LMTs globally could have on the climate, we used a coupled modelling system that we developed, consisting of **EC-Earth3-CC** and **LandSHIFT-G**.

But we also used a range of different models over the course of the project, to answer

different research questions. Here's a quick summary of the various models we used, and what they are good for.

Further reading

- **Journal Articles**
 - A8, A9, A14, A15, A16, A18, A20
- **Deliverables**
 - B13, B15, B17

EC-EARTH3-CC & LANDSHIFT-G

- **What It Does:** It simulates the Earth's climate system by modelling interactions between the atmosphere, oceans, land, and biosphere. It captures feedback processes between climate change and carbon dioxide levels, like changes in vegetation, soil carbon, and ocean carbon uptake.
- **What its good for:** It is particularly useful for studying scenarios related to climate policies, carbon budgets, and ecosystem responses under changing climate conditions.
- **Where we used it:** Globally.

DAYCENT

- **What it does:** It uses information about the weather, the type of soil, and what the land is used for to predict how much carbon dioxide is released or absorbed by the land over time.
- **What its good for:** Understanding how specific land use practices change the soil, especially with respect to levels of carbon and nitrogen.
- **Where we've used it:** the Netherlands, Switzerland, Spain, Portugal, Ukraine, Burkina Faso, Kenya, France, Australia.

OTHER MODELS WE USED

ALCES FLOW

- **What it does:** It simulates changes in landscape composition and carbon in response to projected land use changes.
- **What its good for:** Analysing the impacts of various land use scenarios on carbon dynamics and landscape changes.
- **Where we've used it:** The Netherlands, Burkina Faso, Vietnam, Canada, Indonesia, Venezuela, Nepal, Spain, Switzerland.

LANDSHIFT

- **What it does:** It predicts how land use might change over time based on different scenarios of population growth, economic development, and environmental policies.
- **What its good for:** large-scale, long-term predictions. It can help in planning for sustainable development by showing where pressures on land might lead to environmental degradation or loss of habitat.
- **Where we've used it:** Ukraine, Indonesia, Burkina Faso, Switzerland.

E3ME

- **What it does:** It helps us understand how changes in the economy, energy use, and the environment are connected worldwide.
- **What its good for:** Looking at how economy, energy, and environment interact globally. It can predict how green policies or technologies might impact jobs, industries, and emissions.
- **Where we've used it:** The Netherlands, Switzerland, Germany, Sweden.

LEAVING A LEGACY

Legacy is often frustratingly difficult for research projects. Integrating a project's results into future research agendas, and making the argument for their inclusion in actual policy or practice often takes time and effort.

Neither of these are readily available once a project ends and its team disperses.

Here are two of the steps we have taken to ensure our work outlasts the life of the project.

WORKING WITH WOCAT

For the last 30 years, WOCAT has been steadily building a global, open-access, online database for sustainable land management good practices.

Recommended by the UNCCD, this database allows land-users, researchers, and policymakers from around the world to search for practices or approaches that can help improve the long-term productivity and health of their land. With examples from all over the world, it helps address the specific land-use challenges farmers and land-managers are grappling with.

Many of our case study results from places like the Netherlands, Germany, Switzerland, Kenya, Indonesia, Portugal and Spain have been added to the WOCAT database, and will be openly accessible for as long as WOCAT continues to exist. Find them [here](#).

BIOGAS IN UKRAINE

A new biogas initiative in Ukraine grew out of LANDMARC's work – specifically, its introduction of a Ukraine case study. The biogas project builds on LANDMARC's findings by helping create a network of biogas plants powered by agricultural waste.

INTERACTIVE AI TOOL

A first for a Horizon Europe project, we built an interactive AI Tool out of LANDMARC's public deliverables. This tool (called [Ask LANDMARC](#)) makes our work widely accessible by allowing anyone to ask about our whichever of our results they want, at whatever level of detail they prefer. It's open to anyone with a free ChatGPT account. [Try it yourself](#).

ADAPTING TO NEW REALITIES

A STORY OF UKRAINE, LANDMARC, AND BEYOND

2022: AN EMERGENCY RESPONSE

18 MARCH 2022

Natalia Prozorova and her daughter arrive in the Netherlands at the family home of Eise Spijker (JIN, co-coordinator of LANDMARC) for an extended stay.

JUNE 2022:

TU Delft recruits Natalia to work on the LANDMARC project under Dr. Jenny Lieu (LANDMARC coordinator and assistant professor at TU Delft).

2022-2023: ACTIVE RESEARCH

COLLABORATION

Yurii Zalavskiy from the ISSAR travels to the University of Kassel to use the land-use model LandSHIFT to assess risks, co-benefits and trade-offs for different LMTs in Ukraine.

SIMULATION MODELLING

DayCent simulations (by Moritz Laub from ETHz) indicate a clear carbon sequestration benefit from organic agriculture and reduced tillage.

LANDshift simulations (by the team from Uni Kassel and Yurii Zalavskiy from ISSAR) indicate that redistributing agricultural production to more productive soils in the western and central parts, would mean have benefits.

EARTH OBSERVATION

ArgrolInsider's SmartAG carbon monitoring tool, in combination with soil microbial analysis (by Bioclear Earth) estimates the soil CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes and carbon accumulation potential in black soils in the Forest-Steppe zone of Ukraine under organic (organic cropping and reduced tillage) and conventional land and crop management.

2023-2024: THE FUTURE

BIOGAS & BIOMETHANE FOR UKRAINE

Market and business case analysis report on the biogas/biomethane scaling potential in Ukraine. This is funded by the Energy transitions lab of TU Delft and supported by JIN and Adverio Engineering from The Netherlands.

EU LIFE-2024-CET PROPOSAL

This focuses on policies, governance and data systems for biomethane systems in Finland, Ukraine, The Netherlands and the EU.

NEW FELLOWSHIP

Natalia Prozorova receives a 2-year research fellowship grant at TU Delft from the MSC4Ukraine scheme. It focuses on: *'Improving the resilience of Ukrainian agriculture for post-war soil restoration and carbon mitigation'*.

NEW PROPOSAL

A four-year project proposal is submitted to the Hoizon 2024 Scheme the to accelerate the adoption of carbon farming practices in the EU that are critical for mitigating climate change and improving soil health.

A heartfelt thanks to all LANDMARC partners who supported the collaborative research in and with Ukrainian stakeholders and, especially, to Eise, his family, and Jenny for their incredible kindness and support."

-- Natalia Prozorova

IT'S THE PEOPLE THAT MAKE THE PARTY

WHY WE DIDN'T STUDY SOLUTIONS FOR A WORLD WE DON'T LIVE IN

How many times have we heard it said?

Researchers live in ivory towers, coming up with ideas that belong in a distant utopia, disconnected from reality.

At first glance, they might have a point. But at LANDMARC, we decided to challenge that narrative—not by dreaming up solutions for a fantasy world but by grounding our work in the rich, often messy reality of everyday life.

Our mission was ambitious. We had discussions with 540 stakeholders across the globe— in 14 countries, spanning continents and cultures.

These weren't just academics or policy wonks. They were farmers battling unpredictable weather, indigenous communities preserving ancestral lands, regional governments grappling with climate policy, and professional associations balancing environmental concerns with economic imperatives.

Together, their voices became the foundation of our research, shaping our analyses and simulations with insights only direct experience can provide.

It wasn't always easy. Translating across languages, cultures, and areas of expertise was a massive effort. But what emerged was a tapestry of knowledge woven from a shared understanding of the challenges we face—and how we might overcome them.

Adapting to survive, mitigating for the future

For us, as sustainability scientists, climate change mitigation is often the north star guiding our efforts. Yet, as we listened to these communities, another truth emerged: while mitigation matters, adaptation is often the more immediate concern.

In regions where droughts parch the soil and heavy rains wreak havoc on crops, people aren't just waiting for global carbon emissions to drop. They're building resilience now—adapting their practices, retrofitting infrastructure, and innovating to endure the onslaught of extreme weather events.

But here's the twist: adaptation and mitigation aren't mutually exclusive. In fact, many of the solutions people are using to adapt are also powerful tools for tackling the root causes of climate change.

Take agroforestry, for example. Integrating trees into farmland does more than protect crops from harsh winds and searing heat. Those trees double as carbon sinks, capturing CO₂ from the atmosphere. Similarly, organic farming doesn't just build healthier soils; it locks carbon underground while fostering a thriving ecosystem of microorganisms that make crops more resilient to floods and droughts alike.

The power of perspective

At LANDMARC, we understand that sustainability isn't just about saving the planet—it's about creating a better, more equitable world for everyone.

This perspective has resonated far beyond academic circles. Over 1.4 million people have engaged with LANDMARC's outputs over the past four years, a testament to the project's ability to connect science with the lives of everyday people.

More than just a climate solution, LANDMARC's work is helping redefine how we approach carbon markets and nature-based solutions. These aren't just tools for capturing CO₂; they're holistic strategies that offer cascading benefits—from preserving biodiversity to strengthening food systems and fortifying communities against the

impacts of a warming planet.

A call to action

As we look to the future, the lessons of LANDMARC remind us that tackling climate change is not just about cutting emissions or setting targets. It's about listening, learning, and building partnerships that ground our efforts in the complex realities of life on Earth.

The solutions we need aren't fantasies—they're already here, growing in the fields, shaded by trees, and nurtured by the hands of people who know the land better than anyone. It's up to all of us to nurture and scale these practices, transforming them from local innovations into global movements.

In the end, the reality we create will be the legacy we leave behind—a world shaped not just by ideas, but by action.

More reading

- **Journal Articles**
 - A2, A5, A13, A17
- **Deliverables**
 - B3, B11, B16
- **Explainers**
 - C10, C11, C15

PUBLICATIONS

PEER REVIEWED

A1

An alert system for Seasonal Fire probability forecast for South American Protected Areas (2021)

Anderson, et al

A2

To Burn or not to Burn? The History behind the Construction of a New Paradigm of Fire Management in Venezuela through Interculturality (2021)

Bilbao, et al

A3

Historical fire ecology and its effect on vegetation dynamics of the Lagunas de Montebello National Park, Chiapas, México. (2021)

Ponce-Calderón, et al.

A4

Closing an open balance: The impact of increased tree harvest on forest carbon (2022)

Soimakallio, et al

A5

Traditional knowledge of fire use by islanders in the Paraná Delta, Argentina (2022)

Millán, et al.

A6

The smoke clears... Global experiences in tropical fire management. (2022)

Pasiecznik, et al.

A7

An intercultural vision for integrated fire management in Venezuela. (2022)

Bilbao, et al

A8

Projected Changes in Hot, Dry, and Compound Hot-Dry Extremes Over Global Land Regions (2023)

Paolo De Luca, Markus Donat.

A9

Managing soil organic carbon in tropical agroecosystems: evidence from four long-term experiments in Kenya (2023)

Laub, et al.

A10

Potentials and barriers to land-based mitigation technologies and practices (LMTs)—a review (2023)

Karki, et al

A11

Investigating biochar as a net-negative emissions strategy in Colombia: Potentials, costs, and barriers (2023)

Torres-Morales, et al.

A12

Capacity gaps in land-based mitigation technologies and practices: A first stock take (2023)

Bößner, et al.

A13

Inclusive stakeholder engagement for equitable knowledge co-production (2023)

Lieu, et al

A14

How Credibly Do CMIP6 Simulations Capture Historical Mean and Extreme Precipitation Changes? (2023)

Donat, et al.

A15

Constraining decadal variability regionally improves near-term projections of hot, cold and dry extremes (2023)

De Luca, et al.

A16

Large spread in interannual variance of atmospheric CO2 concentration across CMIP6 Earth System Models (2023)

Martín-Gómez, et al

A17

Community-Based Monitoring for Meaningful Incorporation of Indigenous and Local Knowledge (2023)

Sidorova and Virla

A18

Observed Global Changes in Sector-Relevant Climate Extremes Indices—An Extension to HadEX3 (2024)

Dunn, et al.

A19

A Novel Approach to Mapping and Monitoring Land Carbon Sinks: A Case Study in Burkina Faso (2024)

Ahmed, et al.

A20

Observation-constrained projections reveal longer-than-expected dry spells (2024)

Petrova, et al.

A21

Initial soil carbon losses may offset decades of biomass carbon accumulation in Mediterranean afforestation (2024)

Renna, et al.

PROJECT DELIVERABLES

B1 Improved GHG Monitoring Practices (Deliverable 2.4)

Hannes Böttcher & Anke Benndorf

B2 Potential of Carbon Offsetting Schemes (Deliverable 2.5)

Eise Spijker

B3 County Case Study Scaling Scenarios (Deliverable D2.6)

Eise Spijker & Carlos Gil Picón

B4 Land-based Mitigation in Case Study Countries (Deliverable 2.9)

Eise Spijker & Malte Renz

B5 In-situ measurements data collection report (Deliverable 3.2)

Afnan Suleiman & Eline Keuning

B6 Prototype Model-Observation Systems to Estimate Negative Emissions (Deliverable D3.3)

Mohamed Ahmed & Annemarie Klaasse

B7 Best Management Practices Guide (Deliverable 3.5)

Pilar Martín & Federico Julián

B8 Climate Risk Assessment and Initial Risk Management Plan (Deliverable 4.1)

Carlos Gil Picón & Eise Spijker

B9 The Climate Sensitivity of LMTs (Deliverable 4.2)

José Rafael Marques da Silva, Patrícia Lourenço, Luís Paixão, Folkert Boersma & Jüliette Anema

B10 Atlas on Climate Risk (Deliverable 4.3)

Markus Donat

B11 Results from risk, co-benefit and trade-off assessment (Deliverable 5.2)

David Ismangil & Jenny Lieu

B12 Land-based Mitigation Policies: Status and Challenges (Deliverable 5.4)

Lokendra Karki

B13 E3ME Model Simulations (Deliverable 5.5)

Eva Alexandri & Michael McGovern

B14 Regional Engagement for Global Impact (Deliverable 6.2)

Francis X. Johnson

B15 Quantification of LMT scaling scenarios (Deliverable 6.3)

Rüdiger Schaldach & Florian Wimmer

B16 Capacity Needs Assessment for Successful LMT Implementation and Scaling (Deliverable 6.4)

Stefan Bößner

B17 Testing Preliminary Scenario Simulations (Deliverable 7.1)

Rüdiger Schaldach

CONSULTATIONS, EXPLAINERS, HUBS

POLICY CONSULTATIONS AND WORKING PAPERS

C1

Evidence to UK Negative Emissions Inquiry

Benjamin Sovakool & Ed Dearnley

C2

EU Carbon Removal Certification Consultation

Eise Spijker

C3

Prospects and challenges for implementing land-based climate change mitigation in support of carbon dioxide removal in China

Mathieu Mal, Huiling Zhu & Francis X. Johnson

INFORMAL ARTICLES & EXPLAINERS

C4

Research advances means to expand the role of land in climate change strategies

Jenny Lieu & Eise Spijker

C5

Could Negative Emissions Actually Help Curb Climate Change?

Eise Spijker

C6

COP26 in Glasgow delivered rules for international carbon markets – how good or bad are they?

Lambert Schneider

C7

Molecular biology enlightening soil microbes in the process of carbon sequestration

Johanna Ek Wahlqvist

C8

Nature-based negative emissions; beyond carbon sequestration

Carlos Gil Picón & Richard Flockemann

C9

Planting more trees isn't the be-all and end-all for carbon offsetting. Here's why.

Valeria Renna & Richard Flockemann

C10

Producing research that's useful to policy-makers, businesses, and land managers

Rüdiger Schaldach & Richard Flockemann

C11

Using land to fight climate change (video)

Richard Flockemann

C12

A Guide for Soil Health and Fertility for Maize Production in Kenya

Patrick Nyaga, Rebecca Yegon, Mortiz Laub & Johan Six

POLICY BRIEFS

C13

On the Complementarity of Climate Incentive Schemes

Eise Spijker

C14

Strengthening Land-Based Mitigation Technologies in Indonesia

Su-re.co

INSIGHT HUBS

C15

Ask LANDMARC Interactive AI Tool

Richard Flockemann

C16

LANDMARC's Zenodo Community

C16

LANDMARC's WOCAT Results

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ABOUT THIS RESEARCH

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